

An Investigation into the Emotional Intelligence of Ranchi's 12th Grade Students

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Publication Date: 2025/02/22

Abstract:

➤ Aim

The purpose of the present study is to An investigation into the emotional intelligence of Ranchi's 12th grade students.

➤ Method

The stratified random sampling approach was used to choose the samples.80 students were chosen at random from various Ranchi colleges and schools for that. Data was gathered using the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory, which was created by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Mrs. Shubra Mangal (2004), as well as a personal data questionnaire. Anova, Mean, SD, and Percentage were used to treat the data.

➤ Result

Across the entire study group, 46.25% of the students exhibited the average level of emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence was higher among male students (52.5%) than female students (37.5%). Muslim pupils showed a higher percentage of average emotional intelligence (55%) than their Hindu counterparts (40%). Religion had no effect on emotional intelligence, and gender had a statistically significant F value of 3.98 at the 0.05 level. With a F value of 0.10, the interaction between gender and religion was not statistically significant.

➤ Conclusion

The group as a whole showed varied levels of emotional intelligence. There was no statistically significant difference in emotional intelligence between gender and religion. Religion has little effect on emotional intelligence, but gender does.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Class 12 Students, Religion, And Gender.

How to Cite: Komal Kumari. (2025). An Investigation into the Emotional Intelligence of Ranchi's 12th Grade Students. International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology, 10(1), 2765-2769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14908861>.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important and most discussed facets of human nature is emotional intelligence. In addition to intelligence quotient, people are now evaluated on their emotional quotient.

Everyone is affected, including adults, teenagers, and newborns. Most students who are enrolled in undergraduate programs are in their late teens. Many different types of emotions show up at this age. Young children need to learn how to deal with situations that involve emotional changes, how to be more aware of their emotions, and how emotions affect whether they succeed or fail in life. The student's field of study also has an impact on their emotional intelligence.

In many circumstances in daily life, people's behavior and reactions are greatly influenced by their emotions. Being able to identify our own emotions as well as those of others, inspire ourselves, and effectively control our emotions and those of others is essential in our daily life. The capacity to monitor emotions in real time is essential for psychological insight and self-awareness (Sowmya & Betsur, 2010). Good feelings improve the quality of life and help to control emotional problems and disruptions. Emotional intelligence can help people succeed in life more than those who only acquire high levels of intellectual intelligence [Goleman, 1998]. Emotionally calm people are more capable of handling difficulties than emotionally disturbed ones. In many circumstances in daily life, people's behavior and reactions are greatly influenced by their emotions. Being able to identify our own emotions as well as those of others, inspire ourselves, and effectively control our emotions and those of others is essential in our daily life. The capacity to monitor

emotions in real time is essential for psychological insight and self-awareness (Sowmya & Betsur, 2010). Good feelings improve the quality of life and help to control emotional problems and disruptions. Emotional intelligence can help people succeed in life more than those who only acquire high levels of intellectual intelligence [Goleman, 1998]. An emotionally secure individual may handle difficulties more effectively than an emotionally disturbed person. places in the brain.

Since humans are emotional creatures, a teacher who is adept at utilizing them would have devoted students (Negi, 2011). They are emotionally intelligent, which means they have the emotional skills required for teamwork (Kukreti & Balodi, 2011). Success in any activity has long been thought to be determined by one's intelligence quotient (IQ), which is measured by academic performance, examinations passed, grades earned, and other factors. Stated differently, doing well in school. Research demonstrating that people may use their emotions to enhance their reasoning and thinking sparked the field of emotional intelligence studies in the early 1990s.

Today, the majority of people in organizations and educational institutions are dealing with a lack of trust, startling uncertainty, limited innovation, a gap between managers and coworkers, a lack of loyalty, a sense of unity, and dedication, and more (Murphy, 2006). Students' failures are caused by a lack of fundamental emotional intelligence abilities rather than a lack of intelligence to finish college coursework. They blame others for their failure or become too critical of themselves. Emotional intelligence requires that these issues be acknowledged and comprehended in educational institutions and businesses.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Numerous studies have been conducted on this variable; a handful that were deemed pertinent are listed here. In their 2016 study, Huda and Abdullah Mohsen Gashoah examined how different teaching strategies affected the development of students' emotional intelligence and academic performance in science classes. The findings indicate a positive correlation between the Control Group's educational outcome and emotional intelligence. There is a negative correlation between educational outcomes and the emotional intelligence of the experimental group. In class XI, Rekha Verma (2014) examined the emotional intelligence and self-concept adjustment of rural and urban teens in connection to their academic achievement. Academic success and emotional intelligence are significantly positively correlated for all pupils.

Preeti Bhadouria conducted study on the relationship between high school students' academic performance and their personality and emotional intelligence in 2014. It has been established that there is a connection between high school students' academic success and emotional intelligence. According to Najib Ahmad Marzuki et al. (2012), pupils attending boarding schools exhibit higher levels of emotional intelligence than those attending religious and daily high

schools. Louis and Emerson (2012) investigated the adolescent adjustment of high school pupils. According to A Brief Report on Mid-Adolescence Transitioning, emotional, social, and academic difficulties were present for both boys and girls. However, no discernible gender differences were seen. When Jayawerdana and Jayawerdana (2012) examined the emotional intelligence of students majoring in science, economy, and the arts, they found that students majoring in science had higher emotional intelligence than students majoring in economy and the arts.

In 2005, Katyal and Awasthi studied "Gender Differences in Emotional Intelligence among Adolescents of Chandigarh." According to the findings, boys and girls had different mean emotional intelligence scores, with girls scoring higher than boys. A 2004 study by Tiwari and Srivastava was titled "College and Emotional Intelligence Development." The results of the study showed that while grade and teaching medium had minimal effect on emotional intelligence, gender significantly affected the different aspects of emotional intelligence. Drago (2004) looked into the relationship between non-traditional college students' academic achievement and emotional intelligence. Age, cognitive ability, and student GPA were all found to be substantially correlated with emotional intelligence. . In a study on the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic accomplishment conducted by AbiSamra (2000), it was discovered that students with high grade point averages were emotionally more intelligent than those with low grade point averages.

III. METHODS

A. Objectives

- To investigate the emotional intelligence scores of Ranchi's class 12 Muslim, Hindu, and male students.
- To investigate how gender and religion affect Ranchi class 12 students' emotional intelligence both directly and in combination.

B. Hypotheses

- Both the overall sample and the gender and religious subgroups will have different emotional intelligence scores.
- The emotional intelligence of Ranchi's class 12 students will not be much impacted by gender or religion, either directly or indirectly.

C. Research Design

The sample was chosen from several colleges and schools in Ranchi using the stratified random selection technique. There were four religious and gender-based strata. 20 cases were chosen from each stratum, for a total of 80 samples. The suggested study's sample was derived using a $2 \times 2 = 4$ Factorial design. The basis for the stratification was:

- Gender-2(Boy and Girl)
- Religion (Hindu and Muslim)

➤ *Tools*

• *Personal data questionnaire (PDQ)*

To gather information, the investigator will create a personal data questionnaire. where pertinent data about the sampling criteria, including the individuals' age, gender, education, religion, family income, and residential history, will be gathered.

• *Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII)*

The Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory was developed and standardized by Dr. S. K. Mangal and Mrs. Subhra Mangal (2004). This inventory was developed for use with Hindi and English-speaking students who are 16 years of age or older in order to assess students' emotional intelligence in relation to four areas or aspects of emotional intelligence: intra-personal awareness (own emotions), inter-personal awareness (others emotions), intra-personal management (own emotions), and inter-personal management (others emotions). A yes-or-no response is required for 25 items from each of the four categories, for a total of 100 items. The test's reliability was evaluated using the "Split-half method," the "Test-retest method," and the KR formula-20. The results indicated that it

was significantly good (.89,.90, and.92, respectively). The validity of the scale was.662.

• *Procedure*

Samples were chosen from Ranchi town's various colleges and schools. Twenty pupils were chosen for each group. The chosen sample was given a personal data questionnaire and the study instrument Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory. After completing the questionnaire, the individuals' emotional intelligence was assessed. Each participant received a score of one based on whether they answered "yes" or "no." The degree of emotional intelligence will increase with a lower score.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The hypothesis was graded and statistically assessed using percentage, mean, SD, and Anova. The data can be examined using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The hypothesis can be tested using the respondents' Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory response sheets. Table 1 displays the results of SPSS.

Table 1: Level of Emotional Intelligence among Total Sample

Group	Very Good		Good		Average		Poor		Very Poor	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Total sample	9	11.25	4	5	37	46.25	17	21.25	13	16.25

• *Note.* Total sample= 80. Very Good=88 and Above, Good=75-87, Average=61-74, Poor=48-60, Very Poor=47 and Below:

Nine (11.25%) of the 80 students were very good, and four (5%), were good. Of the college students, 37 (46.25%) had medium emotional intelligence, 17 (21.25%) had bad emotional intelligence, and 13 (16.25%) had extremely low emotional intelligence.

➤ *Sample Sub-groups based of Gender*

Table 2: Level of Emotional Intelligence among Sample Sub-Group based on Gender

	Very Good		Good		Average		Poor		Very Poor		Group
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	
Boy Students	4	10	4	10	21	52.5	8	20	3	7.5	
Girls Students	5	6.25	2	5	15	37.5	8	20	10	25	

• *Note.* Total sample= 80 (n= 40 for each groups) Very Good=88 and Above, Good=75-87, Average=61- 74, Poor=48-60, Very Poor=47 and below.

Table 2 makes it clear that among college students, both male and female, the percentage of those with very strong emotional intelligence was 4 (10%). Compared to female students, who had a decent emotional intelligence score of 5%, male students had a higher score of 6.25%. The average

emotional intelligence score of male students was higher at 21 (52.5%) than that of female students, who scored 15 (37.5%). However, the same proportion of college students— 7.5% of both boys and girls—had low emotional intelligence. The emotional intelligence score of female students was significantly lower at 10 (25%) than that of male students at 2 (5%).

Thus, the hypothesis that "The levels of emotional intelligence will vary in the total sample and sub-groups based on gender and religion" was accepted in the context of

sample sub-groups based on gender. Therefore, one could argue that emotional intelligence varies between boys and girls.

➤ *Sample Sub-groups based of Religion*

Table 3: Level of Emotional Intelligence among Sample Sub-Group based on Religion

	Very Good		Good		Average		Poor		Very Poor Group	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Hindu Students	6	15	4	10	16	40	6	15	8	20
Muslim Students	2	5	2	5	22	55	10	25	4	10

- Note. Total sample= 80 (*n*= 40 for each groups) Very Good=88 and Above, Good=75-87, Average=61- 74, Poor=48-60, Very Poor=47 and below.

2 (5%), Hindu students scored 8 (20%), which is a very low degree of emotional intelligence.

Table 3 makes it clear that a greater percentage of Hindu students (6, or 15%) had very good emotional intelligence than Muslim students (2, or 5%). Compared to Muslim students, who had a decent emotional intelligence score of 5%, Hindu students had a superior score of 10%. The average emotional intelligence score of Hindu students was lower at 16 (40%) than that of Muslim pupils, who scored 22 (55%). However, a higher percentage of Muslim college students (10, or 25%) had low emotional intelligence than Hindu students (8, or 20%). Compared to Muslim pupils, who scored

Therefore, in the context of sample sub-groups based on religion, the hypothesis that "The levels of emotional intelligence will vary in the total sample and sub-groups based on gender and religion" was accepted. Therefore, it may be claimed that there were differences in the prevalence of emotional intelligence between Muslims and Hindus.

The second goal was to examine the separate and combined impacts of religion and gender on emotional intelligence. Anova was used to analyze the data, and table 2 presents the findings.

Table 4: Summary of Two Way ANOVA for Gender and Religion on the Level of Emotional Intelligence

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Gender	801.02	1	801.02	3.98*
Religion	55.22	1	55.22	0.27(NS)
Gender * Religion	0.02	1	0.02	0.10(NS)
Between	856.27 ^a	3	285.42	1.41
Error	7242.70	76	95.30	
Total	8098.98	79		

- Note. df = degree of freedom; dependent variable = emotional intelligence; independent variables = gender and religion; **p*<.05. ***p*<.01; N = 80, ANOVA = analysis of variance. NS = Not significant

Table 2 above illustrates how gender has a major influence on emotional intelligence. At the 0.05 level, the obtained F value of 3.98 was statistically significant. There was no discernible independent impact of religion on emotional intelligence. With a F Value of 0.27, the results were not statistically significant. The gender-religion interactional impact had a non-significant F value of 0.10.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus, "The null hypothesis was that there would be no significant main and interaction influence of gender and religion on the emotional intelligence of college students in Ranchi town." is viewed negatively from a gender perspective.. In the context of religion, it was thus acknowledged that college students, both male and female, have emotional intelligence to differing degrees. As a result, the null hypothesis about the interaction between gender and religion was accepted, and it was discovered that Muslim and Hindu college students possessed emotional intelligence to the same extent. The F-ratio showed no discernible differences in the emotional intelligence levels. Consequently, it was found that college students of both

genders and religions possessed the same level of emotional intelligence.

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